

FUNDING STRATEGIES

in Diamond Open Access publishing

Balancing free access with financial stability is a key challenge for Diamond OA publishers. Here are 8 strategies you can use to secure sustainable funding while ensuring open access, transparency, and independent editorial control.

Diverse funding sources

Relying on a single funding source is risky. Actively seek funding from a mix of local, regional, national, and international sources, to provide a robust financial foundation.

Long-term funding

Prioritise long-term funding from academic institutions, ministries, research funding agencies, and avoid contributions that are tied to individual outputs or groups of authors. This provides financial stability and allows for strategic planning and development.

Shared values

Ensure funding sources align with the values and traditions of the disciplines served. Avoid conflicts of interest and maintain editorial independence.

Clear policies

Publish clear policies for accepting external funding, to ensure transparency and maintain editorial independence.

Sustainability plan

Create a comprehensive sustainability plan outlining the journal's medium-term economic viability.

This plan should include:

- Projected costs and revenue streams.
- Strategies for resource allocation and cost reduction.
- Plans for leveraging shared infrastructure and collaborative partnerships.

Year-on-year cost identification

Plan your annual costs and balance them with expected incomes and in-kind contributions using a tracking system, such as a budget.

Resource sharing and collaboration

Partnering with other institutions, libraries, or service providers can unlock access to resources, expertise, and cost-saving shared services.

National or regional publication portals often provide low- or no-cost publishing infrastructure, reducing the need for additional technical funding.

Strong relationships with host institutions are also crucial for funding (monetary and or in-kind) and support.

Transparency

Transparency is important to build trust and demonstrate integrity. Publish a clear statement about funding sources on the journal website, and include acknowledgement of donations, project funding, and in-kind and voluntary contributions. Indicate any conflicts of interest.